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Nonlinear Absorption Studies of Disperse Orange Doped Polymer Film

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Abstract. Organic materials with substantial third order nonlinearity have become very important to protect the eyes and other sensors in high power laser applications. These materials are mostly based on the principle of reverse saturable absorption (RSA) where absorption cross section for excited state becomes more than the ground state. In such cases transmittance of the material decreases with increase in intensity of laser beam. In this paper, we report the experimental results of Disperse orange-25 dye doped polymer films prepared using hot- press technique. Using open aperture z-scan technique we observe saturable absorption (SA) for disperse orange films at lower intensity and RSA at higher intensity of 532 nm with a 6 ns and 10 Hz Nd:YAG laser beam . We have also studied the nonlinear response and optical limiting nature of the sample with cw and nano -second laser at 532 nm.

1 Introduction

The nonlinear light absorption due to the photoinduced charge transport has been studied in the field of nonlinear optics because of its important role in the construction of passive optical limiters and optical limiting elements in the optical processing systems. Optical limiters are devices that protect sensitive electro-optic sensors against possibly damaging, laser radiation, where the source is of an unknown wavelength or frequency[1]. The transmitted energy should be lower than the damage threshold of the optical sensor. For visible pulses in the nanosecond regime, the damage threshold of human eye is about $0.5 \mu\text{J cm}^{-2}$ on the cornea[2]. The performance specifications for an optical limiter are demanding, requirement of a high in-band transmission in absence of laser radiation, the ability to limit over a large range of pulse lengths from picoseconds to microseconds and a broad-band spectral response that is at least equal to the operating wave band of the sensor it is trying to protect. They also should have reversible protection in which the device should return to the transparent state after laser aggression, chemical, thermal and photo-physical stability[3]. These optical devices rely on one or more of the nonlinear optical mechanisms, which include Excited State Absorption (ESA)[4], Two-Photon Absorption (TPA)[5], Nonlinear Refraction[6], Induced scattering[7], and Photorefracton[8]. Optical limiting is one of the field in which the organic materials are dominating due to the possibility of tailoring their properties in which one may

limit the transmission of intense laser light through a medium using excited state saturable absorption and nonlinear response of molecular media. Organic molecules with highly polarizable π - electrons [9] are of great interest because of their high nonlinear optical response and their potential use as optical limiting media.

Fig. 1 : Molecular Structure of Disperse Orange – 25

Fig. 2 : Linear absorption spectrum of Disperse Orange. $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 468 \text{ nm}$

In this report we present the results of linear and nonlinear optical properties of an acceptor – donor molecule, 3-[N-ethyl-4-(4-nitrophenylazo)phynyl-amino]propionitrile (Disperse Orange 25). This molecule exhibit large reverse saturable absorption (RSA)[10-12], which is considered to be the most important power limiting mechanism. It was shown by model calculations that using materials with high RSA, it is possible to achieve a 10^4 nonlinear attenuation [13]. When a

strong laser pulse propagates through a medium with molecules of high RSA, the population of excited state increases. This increase in population is proportional to the ground state cross section and the excitation photon flux. Consequently, if the excited state cross-section of the material is much higher than that of the ground state, then the effective absorption of the medium will increase significantly and the material will limit the transmission of laser light. The significant requirements for RSA materials which are used in optical limiting devices are [14] : (1) in order to attenuate the power of the incoming light to a safe level, to avoid any damage, the ratio of the excited state absorption and ground state absorption cross-sections, σ_{ex}/σ_{gr} , should be much larger than 1. (2) The material should be relatively high transmission at low intensity light levels. (3) The materials should have broad band spectral response that covers the entire or very large segment of the visible region. (4) The response time must be faster than exciting laser pulses rise time and it should become transparent immediately after the pulse. To design RSA materials which satisfy the above requirements, the absorption spectrum of excited state, the excited state absorption cross section, kinetics of excited state and photochemical mechanism of the molecules must be studied. We have studied the linear, nonlinear optical properties using Z-scan and optical limiting nature of these films in cw and nano second regime at 532 nm. The molecular structure of DO-25 is shown in Fig. 1.

2 Sample Preparation

Commercially available Disperse orange-25 (Aldrich Chemical Co.) is purified by recrystallization twice with spectrograde ethanol and by vacuum sublimation. The purity is determined spectroscopically. Purified chloroform is used as the solvent. To prepare the film, Polymethyl methacrylate – metacrylic acid (PMMA-MA) is used as polymer matrix. PMMA-MA has been chosen as a polymer matrix because of its wide transmission range and easiness of processing. The thin films of disperse orange doped in PMMA-MA are prepared using hot-press technique [15]. Thin films of variable thickness and concentrations are obtained between two glass slides.

3 Linear Optical Properties

The linear absorption spectrum of DO-25 doped in PMMA-MA is measured on a VARIAN Cary UV-vis-IR recording Spectrophotometer. The Figure 2 shows the linear absorption spectrum of the sample. The spectral curve has shown that there is a strong absorption band with peak absorption located at 468 nm with a bandwidth of 100 nm, a medium absorption peaked at 270 nm with a bandwidth of 60 nm and no linear absorption is observed in entire spectral range of 580 to 1200 nm..

4 Nonlinear Optical Properties

Z-scan technique is used to study the nonlinear optical properties of the sample [16]. In Z-scan approach, a single beam is tightly focused into a thin nonlinear medium. The transmittance through a small aperture in the far-field is measured. Figure 6 shows the experimental setup for the measurement of nonlinear. In open

aperture configuration, the system is insensitive to nonlinear refraction, and can be used to measure the nonlinear absorption cross section. Such Z-scan trace with no aperture is expected to be symmetric with respect to the focus ($Z = 0$), where the minimum transmittance (e.g., reverse saturation absorption) or a maximum transmittance (e.g., saturation of absorption) occurs.

Fig. 3 : Experimental set-up used for the measurement of the total transmittance and overall energy conversion efficiencies.

Nonlinear absorption property using z-scan method at 532 nm is shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. Disperse orange has shown saturation absorption at lower input irradiance and then reverse saturation absorption at higher irradiance. To cross check the result, we have also studied the nonlinear absorption property of DO-25 in solution form in a cuvette and the result is shown in Fig. 6. All the results show the nonlinear absorption property of DO-25 due to reverse saturation absorption.

Fig. 4 : Nonlinear absorption of Disperse Orange

Fig. 5 : Z Scan study of Disperse Orange with 4 mm aperture at cw 532 nm.

Fig. 6 : Open aperture Z scan of Disperse Orange in solution

5 Conclusion

We have prepared and characterized the nonlinear optical properties of disperse orange-25 in PMMA-MA polymer matrix. Good films are prepared without any crack using hot-press technique. Linear absorption and nonlinear absorption using z-scan are studied. Disperse orange has shown saturation absorption at lower input irradiance and then reverse saturation absorption at higher irradiance. Further detailed study on excited state absorption coefficient and the optical limiting behavior of the samples in entire spectral region are under investigation.

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